

SAJPCI

Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)

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The Editor-in-Chief

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Navigating Retirement without a Safety Net: Exploring Household size, Marital status, Family Structure and Religion as Predictors of Retirement Planning Behaviour among Older self-employed in Ilorin

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Abstract

Retirement planning among self-employed adults remains a critical but understudied concern in Nigeria, where informal-sector workers constitute the majority of the labour force yet have limited access to structured pension schemes. Despite increasing economic vulnerability among older self-employed individuals, empirical evidence explaining how socio-demographic factors shape retirement planning behaviour within this population is still scarce. This study therefore investigated the influence of household size, marital status, family structure, and religion on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed adults in Ilorin, Nigeria. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 150 purposive selected participants aged 50 years and above. Retirement planning behaviour was measured using the 15-item Retirement Planning Behaviour Scale. Simple and multiple linear regression analyses were used to test the hypotheses. Results showed that larger household size significantly have higher retirement planning behaviour ($\beta = 0.32, p < .01$), Marital status was a partial predictor ($F(3,145) = 3.03, p < .01$), with divorced individuals reporting significantly lower planning ($\beta = -0.18, p < .05$), Family structure did not significantly predict retirement planning ($p > .05$). Religion, however, emerged as a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.14, p < .01$), with Muslim participants reporting higher retirement planning behaviour compared to their Christian counterparts. The joint model revealed that all four socio-demographic factors collectively explained 16% of the variance in retirement planning behaviour ($R = .40, R^2 = .16, F(4,143) = 6.97, p < .01$). The findings highlight the role of family responsibilities, marital transitions, and religious affiliation in shaping retirement planning among older self-employed Nigerians and underscore the need for context-sensitive financial education and policy interventions tailored to the informal sector.

Keywords: Household Size, Marital status, Family Structure, Religion, Retirement Planning Behaviour.

Introduction

Retirement varies from individual to individual often involving identification of sources of income, estimating future costs, initiating a savings strategy while also managing for risks simultaneously. It extends beyond financial matters and includes all areas of one's life, including the establishment of goals for retirement income and determining the essential methods to achieve those objectives (Julia-Kagan, 2023). Retirement also represents a late-career development stage during which individuals continue to grow and transition into new forms of work or lifestyle patterns (Zhan et al., 2023). According to Okechukwu and Ugwu (2011) retirement in Nigeria is classified into three categories: voluntary retirement, which occurs when an employee willingly leaves service; compulsory retirement, initiated by the employer; and mandatory retirement, which follows statutory regulations governing retirement age or years of service. In line with these regulations, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) stipulates that employees in the government parastatals are required to retire after 35 years in service, or 65 years of age or 70 years for specialised professions like the judges and professor in a recognised university (Salisu et al., 2024). Unlike formal-sector employees, self-employed individuals are not covered by the statutory retirement regulations and typically continue working until constrained by declining capacity or economic circumstances. Globally, self-employed individuals continually show lower participation in formal retirement plans compared to salary employees with a statistics of only about 13% of self-employed workers in single-person firm participated in retirement saving plans compared to 75% of traditional employees (OECD, 2019).

In Nigeria, the situation is even more pronounced because most self-employed persons operate in an informal economy. According to the National Pension Commission about 90% of informal sector workers had no pension benefits. Also, earlier figures show 58,800 contributors by the end of 2020 representing only 0.8% of all retirement savings account in Nigeria (Okonkwo, 2021). Given these realities, understanding the determinants of retirement planning behaviour especially among older self-employed individuals essential. Many factors have been investigated on retirement planning behaviour but the roles of socio-demographic factors such as Household size, Marital status, Family structure and Religion, is given less research attention

The United Nations (UN) defines a household as "a small group of persons who share the same living accommodation, who pool some or all of their income and wealth, and who consume certain types of goods and services collectively, mainly housing and food" (United Nations,

1993), but specific practices can vary significantly across countries (Esteve et al., 2024). The size of a household is largely influenced by fertility levels (number of children) and the structure of the co-resident family group, a pattern consistently observed across countries (Esteve et al., 2024). Household characteristics, specifically household size and family composition plays a decisive role in shaping saving and planning behaviour which are core behaviours that ensures a successful retirement planning (Bednarczyk, 2021; Qian, 2024). Larger household typically have immediate consumption needs and greater dependency burdens which limits disposable income available for long-term savings (Etgeton et al., 2023). Conversely, smaller households with fewer dependents may have greater financial flexibility to contribute regularly to their retirement account and plan accordingly towards achieving their retirement goals. In Saharan south of Africa, household size and dependent burden has been identified as major barriers to retirement saving/planning, further emphasizing individuals with larger household size are more likely to experience reoccurring financial demands that affects their capability to plan for retirement thereby amplifying their vulnerability to poverty at old age (Bitana, 2024). According to a study conducted by Moshious Muleya & Silumbe Richard (2026), it findings revealed that household size significantly affects expenditure patterns and saving behaviour which in turn determines behaviour towards retirement planning.

Another factor that may shape retirement planning behaviour is marital status. Recent research shows that married persons often treat retirement as a household level-problem, which changes observed saving patterns i.e married couples are likely to face survivor-risk and joint consumption motives that may alter savings targets in comparison to singles whom plan only for themselves (De Nardi et al., 2021). However, coordinating retirement decisions among married couples can be challenging. A study conducted by Choukhmane et al., (2023), revealed that married couples find it difficult to coordinate their retirement savings efficiently contributing too little due to urgent family needs. On the other hand, singles typically make retirement decisions independently such that they have fewer shared expenses but also lacks the financial support from one's partner, thereby limiting how much they can save and plan for retirement (De Nardi et al., 2021). Another study conducted by Kim et al., (2025), it revealed that marital status exerts a profound influence on retirement planning such that married women typically plan for retirement than unmarried women. Studies have also shown that divorce has a particularly negative effect on retirement planning, this is because couples separation may lead to long term financial crises, such as higher cost of living independently causing the unlikelihood to plan for retirement (Rob Alessie et al., 2025).

The structure of a family unit serves as the fundamental determinant of an individual's economic behaviour and long-term security. According to Chelin(2010), family structure encompasses the organization of partnering relationships with monogamous and polygamous forms representing the most predominant in systems with their distinct financial implications. In monogamous structures, retirement planning is often centered on a centralized 'conjugal fund' where couples accumulate assets for their joint old age, a process highly sensitive to marital dispositions like divorce (Tamborini et al., 2021). In contrast, polygamous structures create a wider network of dependents potentially redirecting financial resources from formal retirement savings towards immediate household needs and investment in a kin-based safety net (Mbama, 2021). A study conducted by Steven et al., (2019), revealed that families with fewer dependents have significantly higher saving behaviours than families with large number of dependents. Adewayi (2020) also found that men in polygamous unions in Nigeria exhibited significantly lower participation in retirement planning schemes than their monogamous peers. emphasizing the influence of family structure on retirement planning. Thus emphasizing that family structure shapes the extent to which individuals prioritize long-term financial goals over immediate household obligations directly influencing retirement planning behaviour.

Beyond family structures religious doctrine provides a powerful moral and institutional framework that shapes long-term financial behaviour that in turn determines retirement planning behaviour. The influence of religion on retirement is multifaceted such that religion affects retirement planning through the rules-each religion has its own teachings about money; the community- which can largely influence one's decisions; beliefs about the future i.e a person's belief about life after death or God's role in their life shapes their planning. In Christianity, the principle of stewardship encourages proactive saving and wealth management, as seen in higher engagement with formal financial services among congregations (Luka et al., 2025). In contrast, Islamic finance is governed by the prohibition of interest(riba), creating a specific demand for sharia compliant to channel their retirement savings causing devout Muslims to abstain from conventional retirement planning (Abdel-Kader & Lin, 2021). Simultaneously, traditionalist belief system is usually centered on ancestors pleasing and communal welfare diverting their resources for formal retirement planning rather into investment in their lineage such as children's education and community rituals further reinforcing their unlikelihood to plan for retirement (Bassa, 2023; Mbiti & Mumoki, 2023).

Theoretically, expectancy theory gives valuable insight in understanding retirement planning behaviour among individuals. It has been defined as the subjective probability (because

individuals differ in their estimations of the relationship between behaviour and outcomes) for the individual's expectation that behaviour would lead to a particular outcome (Vroom, 1964) and as individual's anticipation that his performance will be followed by either success or failure (Atkinson, 1957). The Vroom's Expectancy theory is a well-regarded model in organizational behaviour that explains the relationship between effort, performance, and outcomes in motivating individuals. People are motivated when they believe that their effort will lead to performance, they can see a clear link between performance and certain results and these results are important for them. In relation to retirement planning behaviour, if the individual believes that planning for retirement will certainly lead to having a successful retirement, but place no value on achieving retirement he/she will not be motivated to plan for their retirement. On the other hand, If you place a high value on a goal but expect that the probability of attaining is zero your motivation will again be zero (Buchanan & Huczynski, 1985). The absence of any factor from the theory will lead to lack of motivation for retirement planning.

Against the background of the study, retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals requires immediate attention in Nigeria. Although prior studies (Kim et al., 2025; Ingale et al., 2025; MacLean et al., 2025; Lhaopadchan et al., 2025) have examined various predictors of retirement planning, limited research has explored the combined influence of household size, marital status, family structure, and religion in the context of older self-employed individuals in Nigeria, particularly in Ilorin. Existing studies (Yorose et al., 2025; Ingale et al., 2025; Eboh et al., 2025) often focus on formal-sector workers, leaving a gap in understanding how these demographic and cultural factors shape retirement planning among informal, self-employed populations who constitute the majority of workers in Nigeria and remain the least prepared for retirement hence the need for this study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the predictive influence of household size, marital status family structure and religion on retirement planning behaviour specifically the study hopes to; Investigate the influence of household size on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.

- i. Investigate the predictive role of marital status on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals

- ii. Investigate the predictive impact of family structure on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
- iii. Investigate the predictive effect of religion on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
- iv. Examine the joint predictive roles of household size, marital status, family structure and religion on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.

Research Hypotheses

1. Household size will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
2. Marital status will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
3. Family structure will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
4. Religion will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.
5. Household size, marital status, family structure, religion will jointly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals.

Methods and Materials

Research Approach

This study employed the use of a quantitative research approach as it allows for the quantification of attitudes, opinions, behaviours, and other defined variables and generalize results from a larger sample population and also determines the direction of the relationship between variables across a larger sample.

Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design as it was the most appropriate for this study. This design enabled the collection of data on all relevant variables at a single point in time, allowing for the examination of relationships and patterns among psychological factors and retirement planning within the defined population. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the focus on identifying associations rather than causality, as they are relatively

quick, cost-effective, and efficient for testing hypotheses and estimating prevalence across larger samples (Setia, 2016; Creswell, 2018)

Participants and sampling technique

The study made use of a hundred and fifty respondents (150) older self-employed individuals. Purposive sampling method was also employed, which is appropriate given the specific characteristics required of the study population, i.e being self-employed and within the retirement age range.

Instruments

Demographic Information: This section contains a six-item scale, which seeks information on the respondents' personal information. This includes age, gender, religion, marital status, family type and household size.

Retirement Planning Behaviour Scale: Retirement planning behaviour was measured using the Retirement Planning Behaviour Scale, developed by Goh et al. (2023). It is a 15-item self-report instrument designed to assess individuals' engagement in behaviours related to preparing for retirement. The scale captures a broad range of retirement-related actions, including financial planning, information seeking, goal setting, and psychological preparation for retirement life. It reflects both proactive planning and readiness across multiple domains. Sample item includes: "I have a generally positive outlook on financial future" and "I have a clear understanding of amount for retirement". With each of the 15 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree to 5 = Strongly agree. Total scores are calculated by summing the item responses, with higher total scores reflecting a greater degree of active and intentional retirement planning behaviour, while lower scores suggest limited or insufficient planning activities. The authors reported a high internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.95, indicating that the scale is reliable for assessing behavioural patterns linked to retirement readiness. This study reported a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.72.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria comprised of self-employed individuals aged 50 years and above residing in Ilorin, Kwara State, who were mentally and physically capable of comprehending and responding to the questionnaire items. Exclusion criteria included individuals formally employed by government, private institutions, or NGOs; retired persons no longer actively engaged in self-employment; adults below 50 years of age; non-residents of Ilorin Metropolis; and individuals with severe cognitive impairment or language barriers that could impede effective participation.

Procedure and data analysis

Participants were informed of the study's purpose and assured anonymity to encourage truthful responses. Using purposive sampling, 150 questionnaires were distributed to self-employed older individuals over six weeks in local business shops, markets, hospital patient's caregivers, motorists, and community centers. The hard-copy questionnaires were explained in simple terms to ensure comprehension among participants. Among the distributed questionnaire, 148 were returned yielding a 98.7% response rate. Categorical variables were transformed into dummy variables for analysis. Specifically, each category was coded as 0 and 1 to indicate the presence or absence of a characteristic, such that the reference category was compared against other categorical predictors, the same process applied for multiple level variable. The omitted category serves as the reference group in subsequent analyses and the data was analyzed using the statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.

Ethical Consideration

Participation was voluntary, based on informed consent and that participants could choose to withdraw from the study without any consequence. Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained by collecting no identifiable information of the respondents and storing the data securely and accessible only to the researcher.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents in the Study

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std
Age	50-74yrs			51.54yrs	9.19
Gender	Male	59	39.6		
	Female	90	60.4		
Religion	Christian	90	60.4		
	Islam	59	39.6		
Marital Status	Single	13	8.1		
	Married	122	81.9		
	Divorce	6	4.0		
	Separated	8	5.4		
Family type	Monogamous	124	83.2		
	Polygamous	25	16.8		
House size	1-16			5.42	2.22

The table above shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. In terms of gender 59(39.6%) were male while 90(60.4%) were female. The age ranges from 30-74years with a mean coefficient of 51.54years and standard deviation of 9.19. In terms of religion, it revealed that 90(60.4%) were Christians while the remaining 59(39.6%) were Muslims. The table above further revealed that 13(8.1%) were single, 122(81.9%) were married, 6(4.0%) were divorced and also 8(5.4%) were separated. In terms of family type, 124(83.2%) were in a monogamous family and 25(16.8%) were in a polygamous family. The household size ranges from 1-16 with a mean coefficient of 5.42 and SD of 2.22.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: Household size will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals. The hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression and presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Simple linear regression showing the predictive role of household size on Retirement planning behaviour

Predictor variable	B	SE	β	t	R	R ²	F	P
Household size	1.41	0.28	0.32	4.16	0.32	0.11	17.28	<.01

The simple linear table 2 shows that household size significantly predicts retirement planning behaviour $F(1, 147) = 17.28, p < .001$. This further revealed that household size is a significant predictor of retirement planning behaviour such that an increase in household size increases the likelihood of an individual to plan for retirement. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Marital status will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression and presented on Table 3.

Table 3: Linear Regression analysis showing the predictive role of marital status on Retirement planning behaviour

Variables	β	SE	t	F	P
Constant (married)	51.71	0.70	74.35	3.03	<.01
b ₁ (single)	0.11	1.40	1.40		.16
b ₂ (Divorced)	-0.18	-2.25	-2.25		<.01
b ₃ (Widowed)	-0.10	-1.28	-1.28		.20

1,2 and 3 - Indicates that variables are dummy-coded

The Table 3 indicates that marital status significantly predicts retirement planning behaviour $F(3,145) = 3.03, p < .01$. The intercept has on average an estimated retirement planning score of 51.71 for married individuals. Using married individuals as the reference group, it revealed that divorced individuals reported significantly lower levels of retirement planning than their married counterparts ($\beta = -0.18, t(145) = -2.25, p < .01$). However, no statistically significance

on retirement planning behaviour was found between married individuals and either single ($\beta=0.11$, $t(145) = 1.40$, $p= 0.16$) or widowed individuals ($\beta= -0.10$, $t(145) = -1.28$, $p= 0.20$). Therefore, the hypothesis is hereby partially accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Family structure will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression and presented on Table 4.

Table 4: Linear regression showing the predictive role of family structure on Retirement planning behaviour

Predictor variable	B	SE	t	P
Constant(monogamous)	51.11	0.70	72.82	<.01
b_1 (polygamous)	2.33	1.71	1.38	.18

1 - Indicates the variable is dummy-coded

The Table 3 shows that family structure is not a significant predictor of retirement planning behaviour ($B = 2.33$, $p = 0.18$). Therefore, the hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Religion will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression and presented on Table 5.

Table 5: Linear regression showing the predictive role of religion on Retirement planning behaviour

Predictor variable	B	SE	t	F	P
Constant(Christianity)	50.62	0.82	61.67	2.91	<.01
R_1 (Islam)	2.23	1.31	1.71		<.01

1 - Indicates the variable is dummy-coded

The simple linear table 5 shows that Christians (the reference category) have on average an estimated retirement planning score of 50.62. The overall model explained that religion also significantly predicts retirement planning behaviour $F(1,147) = 2.91$, $p<.01$). Furthermore, the table above indicates that individuals who practice Islamic religion tends to plan for retirement thereby making it a positive predictor of retirement planning behaviour. This further revealed that individuals who identified as practicing Islam reported significantly higher levels of retirement planning compared to their Christian counterparts. religion is a significant predictor

of retirement planning behaviour such that an individual choice of religion increases the likelihood of retirement planning. Therefore, the hypothesis is hereby accepted.

Hypothesis 5: Household size, marital status, family structure, religion will jointly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals. The hypothesis was tested using multiple regression and presented on Table 6.

Table 6: Multiple linear regression showing the joint predictive roles of Household size, marital status, family structure and religion on retirement planning behaviour

Variables	β	t	Sig	R	R ²	F	P
				0.40	0.16	6.97	<.01
Household size	0.30	3.76	0.001				
Marital status	-0.23	-3.02	0.00				
Family structure	0.05	0.67	0.50				
Religion	0.07	0.87	0.07				

The result presented in Table 6 revealed that household size, marital status, family structure and religion jointly and independently predict retirement planning behaviour ($F(1,147) = 6.97, p < .01$). Therefore, the hypothesis is hereby accepted.

Discussion

The study investigated the extent to which household size, marital status, family structure and religion predicts retirement planning behaviour of older self-employed in Ilorin. The study proposed five hypotheses based on the objectives of the study. The first hypothesis, which stated that household size will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals was accepted. This indicates that contrary to the notion that larger households might strain finances and deter long-term savings, a greater number of dependents increases the likelihood of retirement planning. This finding is consistent with Myroniuk et al., (2019) study that revealed that individuals with dependents are more actively engaged in formal and informal retirement saving schemes, driven by the need to avoid being a burden on their children and also to secure the family's welfare. Similarly, the study was in line with Yong et al. (2012) who found that having children is a significant predictor of positive attitudes towards retirement planning further emphasizing that family's responsibility is a powerful motivation for retirement planning. The study finding was in accordance with Hershey et al. (2010) further reinforcing the presence of a working partner and children were significant factors in motivating retirement planning behaviour. The justification for this finding could be interpreted through the lens of heightened perceived responsibility i.e individuals with large household

size may feel the motivation to secure their financial future, which further informs retirement planning in other to be able to provide for their dependents post-retirement.

The second hypothesis, which proposed that marital status will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals, was partially accepted. The findings revealed that divorced individuals exhibited significantly lower levels of retirement planning compared to their married counterparts, while no significant differences were found between married individuals and those who were single or widowed. This result aligns with the findings of Alessie et al. (2025), who argued that divorce undermines financial stability, thereby limiting individuals' ability to engage in retirement planning. Furthermore, the finding that married and single individuals did not differ significantly in retirement planning may indicate that both groups benefit from some level of financial autonomy that supports planning. Married individuals typically benefit from shared economic responsibilities and joint financial decision-making, while singles often develop independent planning habits because they cannot rely on a partner for later-life financial support. This aligns with De Nardi et al. (2021), who emphasized that household decision-making dynamics influence retirement savings patterns, but individual agency still plays a central role in retirement planning. Similarly, Choukhmane et al. (2023) reported that although married couples often struggle with coordinated saving, marriage still offers structural financial advantages through shared contributions and reduced expenses. Therefore, the results of the present study highlight the distinctive vulnerability of divorced individuals and support the view that marital transitions play a critical role in shaping retirement planning behaviour. This suggests that the disruption associated with marital dissolution may impair long-term financial preparation. Divorce often leads to a restructuring of household finances, increased individual expenses, and reduced access to pooled economic resources, all of which weaken the capacity for future-oriented financial planning which further informs retirement planning.

The third hypothesis, which stated that family structure will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals, was rejected. The findings revealed no significant difference in retirement planning between individuals in monogamous and polygamous family structures. This contradicts earlier evidence suggesting that polygamous households typically experience higher dependency burdens that reduce the capacity for long-term savings (Adewayi, 2020; Mbama, 2021). A possible explanation for this inconsistency is that the sampled population consisted of older self-employed individuals who

may have developed adaptive financial strategies over time, irrespective of family structure. Many self-employed workers in Nigeria rely on informal savings mechanisms, diversified income sources, and inter-generational support, which may cushion the expected negative impact of polygamy on retirement planning.

The fourth hypothesis, which posited that religion will significantly predict retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals, was accepted. The findings showed that individuals who identified with the Islamic faith reported higher retirement planning behaviour compared to their Christian counterparts. This result may be understood in the context of religious doctrines that shape financial practices. Islamic financial principles encourage structured financial discipline through zakat obligations, waqf practices, and restrictions on interest-bearing transactions, which may indirectly promote intentional financial management and future-oriented planning. This aligns with Abdel-Kader and Lin (2021), who highlighted that Islamic financial behaviour often prioritizes ethical and disciplined resource allocation. Conversely, some Christian denominations emphasize communal or faith-based support systems, which may reduce the perceived urgency for formal retirement planning (Luka et al., 2025). Additionally, religious communities often influence collective attitudes toward financial security and long-term preparedness. Thus, the study reinforces the notion that religious worldview and doctrinal orientation significantly shape retirement planning behaviour.

The fifth hypothesis, which proposed that household size, marital status, family structure, and religion would jointly predict retirement planning behaviour, was accepted. The joint model explained 16percent of the variance in retirement planning behaviour, indicating that these socio-demographic variables collectively exert meaningful influence on how older self-employed individuals prepare for retirement. Despite some variables not being individually significant (e.g., family structure), their combined effect suggests an interaction influence where demographic factors operate collectively. This is consistent with the expectancy theory (Vroom, 1964), which posits that behavioural motivation arises from a combination of expectations, values, and contextual factors. The combined effects of household size, marital status, family structure, and religious beliefs shape how people think about their future security and how confident they feel about achieving it. These findings show that retirement planning is not driven by one factor alone, but by a mix of structural, relational, and cultural influences working together.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of household size, marital status, family structure, and religion on retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals in Ilorin. The findings revealed that household size, marital status, and religion significantly predicted retirement planning behaviour, while family structure did not exhibit a significant independent influence. Importantly, when considered jointly, the four socio-demographic variables significantly contributed to explaining variations in retirement planning behaviour, highlighting the multidimensional nature of retirement preparation. The results underscore that retirement planning among self-employed individuals is shaped not only by individual preferences but also by relational, cultural, and structural factors. Larger household size appeared to motivate greater retirement planning, likely due to heightened perceived responsibility. Divorced individuals were particularly disadvantaged, reflecting the destabilizing financial consequences of marital dissolution. Religious affiliation also played a role, suggesting that doctrinal beliefs and religious norms influence financial behaviour and long-term planning. Overall, the study contributes to a growing understanding of retirement behaviour among informal-sector workers, an increasingly vulnerable population in Nigeria's current economic context. The findings reinforce the need for tailored interventions that recognize the realities of older self-employed individuals. Strengthening retirement awareness, promoting inclusive pension systems, and addressing the unique vulnerabilities associated with marital transitions and religious orientations are essential steps toward improving retirement security in Nigeria.

Recommendation

In light of the study's findings, several practical and policy-oriented recommendations are proposed to improve retirement planning behaviour among older self-employed individuals in Ilorin. They include;

1. Targeted financial literacy programme should be designed by Government agencies, NGOs, and pension administrators that focus on retirement readiness for older self-employed individuals. Given that household size and marital disruptions influence planning behaviour, such programme should incorporate modules on long-term financial decision making for different household contexts.
2. Pension regulatory institutions should develop more flexible and accessible retirement

schemes tailored to the realities of informal-sector workers. Simplified registration processes, small but frequent contribution options, and mobile-based savings platforms may encourage higher participation in retirement planning.

3. Given the predictive role of religion, integration of religious and community structures such as churches, mosques, and traditional councils could increase awareness and encourage positive attitudes toward retirement planning. Faith leaders can serve as trusted intermediaries for financial education initiatives.

4. The significant influence of household size and marital status on retirement planning underscores the need for government bodies especially the National Pension Commission (PenCom) to redesign micro-pension initiatives to better fit the realities of informal-sector workers. Policies that allow flexible, low-threshold contributions and incentives such as matching contributions or tax benefits could encourage greater participation.

5. Support programme such as financial counselling, divorce-related savings protection guidelines, or post-divorce financial restructuring assistance would help mitigate the long-term financial vulnerabilities associated with marital dissolution. Socio-demographic factors (household size, religion, marital status) should also be considered in designing demographic-specific pension policies. For instance, large-household earners may benefit from policy provisions for family-linked retirement savings or dependents-based incentives.

Limitations and future research direction

Despite the valuable insights gained from this study, several limitations should be acknowledged to provide context for the interpretation of the findings and to guide future research. Firstly, the study employed a cross-sectional research design, which captures data at a single point in time. While this is efficient for identifying associations, it precludes the establishment of causal relationships between the socio-demographic variables and retirement planning behaviour. A longitudinal design would be required to observe how these relationships evolve as individuals approach and enter retirement. Secondly, the use of a purposive sampling technique and the relatively small sample size from a single geographic location (Ilorin) limit the generalization of the findings. The results may not be representative of all older self-employed individuals in Nigeria, particularly those in other regions with different socio-economic and cultural dynamics. Thirdly, the study relied exclusively on self-

report measures, which are susceptible to social desirability bias and inaccuracies in recall. Participants may have over-reported their retirement planning behaviours to present themselves in a more favourable light. Finally, the study focused on a specific set of socio-demographic factors. The omission of other critical variables, such as income level, financial literacy, nature of the self-employed business, and access to formal financial institutions, means that the model may not fully capture the complexity of factors influencing retirement planning behaviour among this population. Future research should incorporate mixed-methods research, including interviews or focus groups, may provide richer insight into motivational factors behind retirement planning.

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